

MiMonte Project - Activities report under WP2, activity 2.b

2.b: Public consultations

1. Public Consultation Pego

Date : 9th April 2026

Place : Biblioteca Pública Municipal, Pego

Time: 18:30-20:00

Number of Participants: 4 people

OUTREACH

We have engaged the community through the following channels:

- Email invites through Pego Viu network
- Publication through PegoViu's social media

OBJECTIVE

The objective of the public consultation was to raise awareness among local landowners about the importance of sustainable forest management and the opportunities it offers — both economically and environmentally. Representatives of PegoViu presented two collaborative agreement models available to participants: a 15-year forest management plan for their plots, and a 40-year reforestation plan, both designed to support landowners in stewarding their land more effectively while contributing to broader ecosystem conservation goals.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in and around Pego who own abandoned lands.

METHODOLOGY / PROCESS

The meeting started off with a general introduction to the local natural environment, the impact of climate change, the recent fires that affected the area of reforestation and learned about the methods for sustainable land management and opportunities that could benefit both the abandoned plots and their landowners. Subsequently, the ground was left open for dialogue about landowners, specifically what were their concerns in taking action in their plots. Participants engaged in a meaningful conversation with mediators.

OUTCOMES

Despite a limited turnout — largely due to the Easter holiday, which prevented several interested participants from attending — the public consultation proved to be a success on multiple fronts.

First, the level of interest was encouraging: a significant number of people responded positively to the invitation but were unable to join due to prior commitments over the holiday period, expressing their regret and genuine interest in participating.

Second, those who did attend engaged actively in the discussion that followed the presentation, sharing their perspectives, raising questions, and contributing meaningfully to the debate.

Finally, the event yielded concrete outcomes. One attendee signed the 40-year agreement on the spot, while another expressed strong interest in signing the 15-year agreement. A third participant — although not a landowner — demonstrated a deep commitment to ecosystem preservation and

offered to contribute professionally as a university professor to PegoViu's work and to any current or future projects concerning this area.

GALLERY

2. Public Consultation Fuente La Reina

Date: 3rd April 2026

Place: Fuente la Reina

Time: 12:00 - 13.30hr

Number of Participants: 12

OUTREACH

Municipality's Whatsapp channel; printed posters on public information boards and at the entry of the village bar; e-mails to participants of previous events; publication in online or facebook wall of <https://247valencia.com/> (<https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=1234956825286480&set=pb.100063165223229.-2207520000&type=3>); Whatsapps to participants of previous events; publication on Desert Leaves' Eventbrite page.

OBJECTIVE

Familiarize people of Fuente La Reina with CSF practices and forest management, so as to convince them to engage in forest management practices.

TARGET GROUP

People living in or owning land in Fuente La Reina

METHODOLOGY

The session included a live visit to the first reforested plot in Fuente la Reina, where project leader Wim Cambien presented the history of the project and the specific actions carried out. Two representatives of Asociación Agrícolas (based in the neighbouring hamlet of Los Calpes) shared their experience of how landowners in their village successfully joined forces to collectively manage small agricultural and forest plots, directly encouraging Fuente la Reina residents to explore a similar model.

OUTCOMES

12 residents gained direct knowledge of local reforestation efforts. Initial contacts were established between Fuente la Reina landowners and Agrícolas representatives, with a view to potentially incorporating Fuente la Reina plots into the land managed by Agrícolas.

GALLERY

3. Public Consultation - Ibiza

Date: 15th April 2025

Place: Ibiza

Time: 12:00 - 13.30hr

Number of Participants: 18

OUTREACH

Email

OBJECTIVE

To bring together forest landowners to review technical forest management instruments and explore opportunities for collaboration with Regenera Natura toward promoting sustainable forest management.

TARGET GROUP

Forest landowners in the area

METHODOLOGY / PROCESS

The session consisted of a participatory meeting format in which technical forest management instruments were reviewed and presented. The possibility of collaboration with Regenera Natura was introduced as a framework for advancing sustainable forest management practices in the area.

OUTCOMES

The session yielded a concrete result: the Rafal Trobat project, currently under active management by the organisation, emerged directly from this meeting. The session successfully engaged 18 landowners and opened a pathway for future collaboration with Regenera Natura.

GALLERY

4. Public Consultation Pego

Date: 10th April 2025

Place: Casa Cultural Pego

Time: 19.30-21hr

Number of Participants: 40

OUTREACH

We have engaged the community through the following channels:

- **Desert Leaves social media channels**
- **Email:** Pego Viu network<, Pego Municipality network and official notification boards
- **Posters:** Posters in public spaces, café's and various other appropriate venues
- **Door-to-Door flyer distribution:** 3000 flyers distributed door to door in Pego Municipality
- **Website Desert Leaves:**

Event registration page, including an optional online questionnaire (in Castellano and Valenciano) for people to fill out to give us more insight and information in order to tailor the workshop to the needs of our target group and to gain a better understanding of the challenges they are facing and the size of the terrains they have. Online registration was made available through the provision of a link and QR codes to a dedicated event page on the Desert Leave website. However, registration was not obligatory for this event as many elderly people do not have digital access or capacity and we did not want to deter land-owners from coming to the event. We received 9 online registrations in total which all included a fully

filled questionnaire.

OBJECTIVE

An interactive public consultation aimed to inform and inspire private owners of 'mostly abandoned' land to work together with Desert Leaves and Pego Viu to either reforest or improve maintenance of their land.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in and around Pego who own abandoned lands.

METHODOLOGY

The session was designed to foster active participation and an open learning environment through group-based interactive activities. After presenting the outcomes of an online questionnaire to set the context, participants formed small groups and were given the following tasks:

- a) Brief introductions: name, place of residence, description of their land (size/type) and current use.
- b) Group discussion: explore potential uses for their land, share ideas, and agree on the top three proposals to present to other groups.
- c) Identify the main challenges: list the four key barriers to implementing these ideas for group discussion.

Following the group activities, a presentation addressed common issues raised, offered solutions, and provided practical information. The session concluded with a Q&A, exchange of contact details, and information about a follow-up Q&A meeting scheduled at the Pego Vui office two weeks later.

5. Public Consultation Fuente La Reina

Date: 18th April 2025

Place: Casa Cultural Pego

Time: 12-13.30hr

Number of Participants: 14

OUTREACH

We have engaged the community through the following channels (note that the majority of property owners are currently residing outside of Fuente la Reina and not in the village itself, they are only returning for special celebrations such as Easter):

- **Desert Leaves social media channels:**
Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook
- **Email:**
Fuente La Reina Municipality network and official notification boards
- **Posters:**
Posters in public spaces, café's and various other appropriate venues
- **Website Desert Leaves:**
Event registration page, including an optional online questionnaire (in Castellano and Valenciano) for people to fill out to give us more insight and information in order to tailor the workshop to the needs of our target group and to gain a better understanding of the challenges they are facing and the size of the terrains they have.

ONLINE REGISTRATION

Online registration was made available through the provision of a link and QR codes to a dedicated event page on the Desert Leave website. However, registration was not obligatory for this event as many elderly people do not have digital access or capacity and we did not want to deter land-owners from coming to the event. We received 2 online registrations in total which both included a fully filled questionnaire.

Follow up emails have been sent out to check in with the participants and provide our contact information for land-owners interested in collaborating with the project.

OBJECTIVE

An interactive public consultation aimed to inform and inspire private owners of 'mostly abandoned' land to work together with Desert Leaves and Pego Viu to either reforest or improve maintenance of their land.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in and around Pego who own abandoned lands.

6. Public Consultation Ibiza

Date: 5th June 2025

Time: 19.30hr

Place: EBUSUS, Ibiza town

Number of Participants: >50

The event, organized by Regenera Natura, was held with the Associació de Propietaris Forestals d'Eivissa (APFDE), the Desert Leaves Foundation, and with the special participation of the Forest Management and Soil Protection Service and the Climate Change and Atmosphere Service of the Balearic Government.

OUTREACH

We have engaged the community through the following channels:

- **Regenatura social media channels:**
Instagram, LinkedIn, Facebook
- **Networks of participating organisations:**
Associació de Propietaris Forestals d'Eivissa (APFDE)
Servei de Gestió Forestal i Protecció del Sòl
Servei de Canvi Climàtic i Atmosfera del Govern Balear
- **Email:**
Ibiza local government
- **Posters:**
Posters in public spaces, café's and various other appropriate venues
- **Website Regenatura:**
Event registration page, including an optional online questionnaire (in Castellano and Valenciano) for people to fill out to give us more insight and information in order to tailor the workshop to the needs of our target group and to gain a better understanding of the challenges they are facing and the size of the terrains they have.

ONLINE REGISTRATION

Online registration was made available through the provision of a link and QR codes to a dedicated event page on the Regenatura website. However, registration was not obligatory for this event as many elderly people do not have digital access or capacity and we did not want to deter land-owners from coming to the event. 45 People registered online of which 19 filled out the form.

OBJECTIVE

An interactive public consultation aimed to inform and inspire private owners of 'mostly abandoned' land to work together with Desert Leaves and Regeneration to either reforest or improve maintenance of their land, with attendees actively engaging in identifying solutions and proposing solutions for a more collaborative and sustainable forest management model.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in Ibiza who own abandoned lands, and interested members of the local

community.
Landowner associations.

IMAGES PUBLIC CONSULTATIONS

**Public Consultation
Ibiza and Pego**